

BA'ZI TRIGONOMETRIK IFODALARNI UCHBURCHAKLAR XOSSALARIDAN FOYDALANIB HISOBLASH.

**Qurbonov Sherzod Rashitovich, Shahrizabz “Temurbeklar maktabi”
harbiy-akademik litseyi matematika fani o’qituvchisi**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada to’g’ri burchakli uchburchaklarda trigonometrik funksiyalar ta’riflaridan va Pifagor teoremasidan foydalanib, ba’zi trigonometrik ifodalarni hisoblashga doir misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: uchburchak, sinus, kosinus, tangens, kotangens, bissektisa, Pifagor teoremasi, ayniyat, formula, burchak.

Bizga ma’lumki, o’tkir burchak trigonometrik funksiyalariga to’g’ri burchakli uchburchakda ta’rif beriladi.

$$\sin A = \frac{BC}{AB} \quad \cos A = \frac{AC}{AB} \quad tgA = \frac{BC}{AC} \quad ctgA = \frac{AC}{BC}$$

Ta’rif. To’g’ri burchakli uchburchakning sinusi deb o’tkir burchak qarshisidagi katetni gipotenuzasiga nisbatiga aytiladi.

To’g’ri burchakli uchburchakning cosinusi deb o’tkir burchakka yopishgan katetni gipotenuzasiga nisbatiga aytiladi.

To’g’ri burchakli uchburchakning tangensi deb o’tkir burchak qarshisidagi

katetni yopishgan katetga nisbatiga aytiladi.

To'g'ri burchakli uchburchakning cotangensi deb o'tkir burchakka yopishgan katetni qarshisidagi katetga nisbatiga aytiladi.

Shuning uchun ham bazi trigonometrik ifodalarni uchburchaklar xossalariidan foydalanib hisoblash qulay va oson bo'ladi. Misollar orqali mavzuni yoritamiz.

1-misol. $\sin\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3} + \arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right)$ ni hisoblang.

Usul.1. Yechish. Bu ifodani hisoblash uchun birinchi asosiy trigonometrik ayniyatlardan foydalanib, quyidagi ifodalarni hisoblaymiz.

$$\cos\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3}\right) = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3}\right)} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{9}} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3}$$

$$\sin\left(\arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right) = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2\left(\arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right)} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{3}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$\sin(\alpha + \beta) = \sin\alpha \cdot \cos\beta + \cos\alpha \cdot \sin\beta$ formuladan foydalanamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \sin\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3} + \arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right) &= \sin\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3}\right) \cdot \cos\left(\arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right) + \cos\left(\arcsin\frac{1}{3}\right) \cdot \sin\left(\arccos\frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}\right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{6}}{3} = \frac{\sqrt{3} + 4\sqrt{3}}{9} = \frac{5\sqrt{3}}{9} \end{aligned}$$

Usul.2. Yechish. Bu ifodani hisoblash uchun to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakning sinusi va cosinusi tariflaridan foydalanamiz.

B

Berilgan $\sin A = \sin(\arcsin \frac{1}{3}) = \frac{1}{3}$ ekanligidan $BC=1$, $AB=3$ deb tanlab olamiz.

Pifagor teoremasidan $AC=2\sqrt{2}$ ni topamiz. U holda $\cos A = \cos(\arcsin \frac{1}{3}) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3}$

bo'ladi. Xuddi shuningdik $\cos A = \cos(\arccos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}) = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}$ ekanligidan $AC=\sqrt{3}$ $AB=3$

deb tanlab olamiz. Pifagor teoremasidan $BC=\sqrt{6}$ ni topamiz. U holda

$\sin A = \sin(\arccos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}) = \frac{\sqrt{6}}{3}$ bo'ladi. $\sin(\alpha + \beta) = \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \beta + \cos \alpha \cdot \sin \beta$ formuladan

foydalanamiz. U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \sin(\arcsin \frac{1}{3} + \arccos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}) &= \sin(\arcsin \frac{1}{3}) \cdot \cos(\arccos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}) + \cos(\arcsin \frac{1}{3}) \cdot \sin(\arccos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{6}}{3} = \frac{\sqrt{3} + 4\sqrt{3}}{9} = \frac{5\sqrt{3}}{9} \end{aligned}$$

2-misol. $tgx=2$ bo'lsa $\frac{2-5\cos x}{6+10\sin x} - \frac{13+3tgx}{10\sin x - 12ctgx}$ ni hisoblang?

Yechish. Bu ifodani hisoblash uchun to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakning sinusi cosinusi tangensi va cotangensi tariflaridan foydalanamiz.

B

C

Berilgan $tgA = tgx = 2$ ekanligidan $BC=2$, $AC=1$ deb tanlab olamiz. Pifagor teoremasidan $AB=\sqrt{5}$ bo'lishini topamiz. U holda $\cos x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$, $\sin x = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$ va $ctgx = \frac{1}{2}$ bo'ladi. Bu qiymatlarni berilgan ifadaga quyib quyidagi natijalarni olamiz.

$$\frac{2-5\cos x}{6+10\sin x} \cdot \frac{13+3tgx}{10\sin x-12ctgx} = \frac{2-5\cdot\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}}{6+10\cdot\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}} \cdot \frac{13+3\cdot 2}{10\cdot\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}-12\cdot\frac{1}{2}} =$$

$$= \frac{2-\sqrt{5}}{6+4\sqrt{5}} \cdot \frac{19}{4\sqrt{5}-6} = \frac{2-\sqrt{5}}{6+4\sqrt{5}} + \frac{19}{6-4\sqrt{5}} = \frac{51-14\sqrt{5}}{36-80} = \frac{14\sqrt{5}-51}{44}$$

3-misol. $\sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\arccos\frac{2}{3}\right)$ hisoblang.

Yechish. Bu ifodani hisoblash uchun to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakning sinusi va cosinusi tariflaridan foydalanamiz.

B

Berilgan $\cos A = \frac{2}{3}$ ekanligidan $AB=3$, $AC=2$ deb tanlab olamiz. Pifagor teoremasidan $BC = \sqrt{5}$ bo'lishini topamiz. U holda A burchak $A = \arccos \frac{2}{3}$ bo'ladi, shu burchakning yarmini sinusini topish kerak. Buning uchun, AD bissektressa o'tkazamiz. Uchburchakdan CD va AD ni topamiz, buning uchun. $CD = x$ deb olsak, $BD = \sqrt{5} - x$ bo'adi. Bissektressa xossasidan foydalanamiz. $AB \cdot DC = AC \cdot DB$ bundan $2 \cdot (\sqrt{5} - x) = 3 \cdot x$. Bu tenglamadan $x = \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{5}$ olamiz. ADC uchburchak uchun

Pifagor teoremasidan $CD = \frac{2\sqrt{30}}{5}$ bo'lishini topamiz. U holda $\sin\left(\frac{1}{2} \arccos \frac{2}{3}\right) = \frac{2\sqrt{30}}{15}$.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, trigonometrik ifodalarni soddalashtirish yoki hisoblashda ularning berilishiga qarab tushuntirsak va geometrik yondashsak maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

Mustaqil yechish uchun misollar.

1. $tg\left[\arccos\left(\frac{4}{7}\right)\right]$ ni hisoblang

2. Hisoblang. $\sin(\operatorname{arctg}(-\sqrt{3}) + \arcsin(-1) - \operatorname{arctg}0)$

3. Hisoblang. $\operatorname{tg}(\operatorname{arctg}(2) + \operatorname{arctg}\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}})$

4. $\operatorname{tg}(\arccos(\frac{1}{5}))$ ni hisoblang

5. $\operatorname{tg}x=3$ bo'lsa, $\frac{21-5\cos x}{16+12\sin x} - \frac{13+3\operatorname{ctgx}}{10\operatorname{ctgx}-15\sin x}$ ni hisoblang?

6. $\operatorname{tg}\frac{x}{2}=2$ bo'lsa, $\sin x$ ni toping?

7. $\operatorname{tg}x=\frac{1}{2}$ bo'lsa, $\frac{2\cos^2 x+3}{3\cos^2 x-2\sin^2 x}$ ni toping?

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

1. H.A. Nasimov Algebra va matematik analiz asoslari. Toshkent 2001 yil
2. K. Muhamedov Elementar matematikadan qo'llanma. Toshkent 1976yil
3. M. Saxayev Elementar matematika masalalari to'plami Toshkent 1977 yil.
- 4.A.G. Sipkin Matematikadan spravochnik. Toshkent 1987yil